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ONE GRADIENT DESCENT METHOD WITH ADAPTED STEP CORRECTION FOR SOLVING ARBITRARY SYSTEMS OF LINEAR ALGEBRAIC EQUATIONS

Abstract

The given paper continues and modifies results of [8], [12] and presents results of work of software product, written in «Visual Basic for Applications», designed for solving various systems of abstract linear algebraic equations. The product is based on optimization descent methods and classical Gauss methods with reduction of arbitrary matrix to triangular form. Developed with the help of synthesis both, classical and optimization, methods, this program is focused on solving an arbitrary system of linear algebraic equations with one unique solution or even infinite number of solutions, and, in the case of absence of some solution, the program calculates so-called discrepancy minimizer.

Keywords and phrases: linear algebra, systems of linear algebraic equations, Gaussian method, Kronecker-Capelli theorem, variational methods, optimization methods, gradient descent method, gradient, anti-gradient, minimizer, discrepancy minimizer.

Introduction. Applied (machine) linear algebra is very extensive and rapidly developing branch of mathematics ([2]) that allows us to take some different look at many of its classical problems. This modern look is demonstrated in this paper. The work presents some results of comparative analysis of classical Gauss method and some modifications of optimization gradient method ([1], [3] – [7], [8], [9] – [11], [12]) for solving arbitrary systems of linear algebraic equations, obtained as result of testing our program, written in «Visual Basic for Applications».

The main part. «Optimization» comes from the same root as «optimal», which means «best». When you optimize something, you are «making it best», as best, as you can. But «best» can vary. For example, if you're a football player, you might want to maximize your running yards and also minimize your fumbles. Both maximizing and minimizing are types of optimization problems. Mathematical optimization is sort of art of finding best solutions to difficult problems, from organizing movements of planes in large airports to placement of windmills. Various mathematical techniques are employed to solve optimization problems, and your choice of method often depends on your problem's characteristics.

Gradient descent methods are quite powerful tools for solving various optimization problems. The main disadvantage of these methods is a bit limited scope of applicability. Using gradient methods, it is possible to find solution to any problem of nonlinear programming. However, in the most general case, with the help of these methods it is possible to find the point of local extremum. Therefore, it is more advisable to use gradient methods to find solutions to programming problems, where every local extremum is simultaneously global. The process of finding a solution with the help

of gradient methods consists in fact that, starting from some certain point, sequential transition to some other points is carried out until necessary acceptable solution to original problem under consideration is identified.

According to the Gauss method of sequential exclusion of unknowns, when solving an arbitrary system from m linear algebraic equations with n unknowns of the form

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + \dots + a_{1n}x_n = b_1, \\ a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2 + \dots + a_{2n}x_n = b_2, \\ \dots, \\ a_{m1}x_1 + a_{m2}x_2 + \dots + a_{mn}x_n = b_m, \end{cases}$$

which is given in vector form by the equation

$$A\vec{x} = \vec{b},$$

where

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn} \end{pmatrix} = A_{m \times n},$$

$$\vec{b} = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ \dots \\ b_m \end{pmatrix} = B_{m \times 1},$$

$$\vec{x} = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ \dots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix} = X_{n \times 1}$$

as result of so-called forward stroke, this system is reduced to equivalent stepwise form, by which it is possible to determine whether there is any solution, it is the only one or there are infinitely many of them. Main essence of gradient descent method is that the solution of this system is reduced to finding extremum (minimum) \vec{x}^* of the following functional

$$f(\vec{x}) = (A\vec{x} - \vec{b}, A\vec{x} - \vec{b}) = \|A\vec{x} - \vec{b}\|^2, A \in \mathbf{R}^{m \times n}, \vec{b} \in \mathbf{R}^m, m \leq n,$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Euclidean norm, (\cdot, \cdot) – Cartesian product. This minimum is achieved for exact solution $\vec{x}^* \in \mathbf{R}^n$ of the system under consideration.

The method consists in constructing one sequence of points $\{\vec{x}_k\}_{k \geq 0}$, converging to so-called minimizer, that is, to exact solution \vec{x}^* , for which the condition

$$f(\vec{x}_{k+1}) \leq f(\vec{x}_k), \quad k \geq 0,$$

is true, using the following recurrent formula

$$\vec{x}_{k+1} = \vec{x}_k - \lambda_k \cdot \text{grad}(f(\vec{x}_k)), \quad \lambda_k > 0, \quad k = 0; 1; 2; \dots,$$

where initial approximation \vec{x}_0 is chosen in arbitrary way. Geometric interpretation of this method for the case $\lambda_k = \text{const}$, $k \geq 0$, is shown in the figure below.

Fig. 1. Schematic example of gradient descent method for the case $\lambda_k = \text{const}$, $k \geq 0$

The result of variational part of the program is solution of the system under consideration, found by the proposed gradient descent method.

The result of the Gauss method is some conclusion about solvability or unsolvability of the system, obtained after application of the Kronecker-Capelli theorem from classical algebra to the reduced triangular system.

When starting the program, user sees the window «Solving SLAE by variational method». He clicks on the «SLAE solution» button, after it the «Data entry» dialog box appears. Here he chooses which way to set the coefficients of the main system and the column of its free terms: enter manually or give this choice to the program, that is, fill in automatically (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. User chooses exactly how to enter the coefficients

If user prefers manual input of all data, then after clicking on the «OK» button, dialog boxes appears where he will be asked to enter dimension (number of rows and number of columns, that is, number of arguments) of necessary system of linear algebraic equations (SLAE), the coefficients of the matrix of the main

system, as well as the column of free terms (fig. 3). After that the system under consideration appears on the worksheet (upper left corner) and some summary of the Gauss method (fig. 4).

Fig. 3. User enters the data: the coefficients of the system and the column of its free terms

Fig. 4. The solved system and obtained summary of the Gauss method

Note that the program contributes to correct processing of data received from user by «filtering» information and reporting possible accidental errors made during input. So, if user enters some invalid character instead of necessary numeric one, the next «signal» dialog box, indicating an error, is displayed (fig. 5).

Fig. 5. User has mistakenly entered data in the wrong format

After the program has showed user finally found solution, he is asked either to continue working by clicking on «Yes» button, or to complete it by clicking on «No» button (fig. 6).

Fig. 6. User chooses what to do next: to continue or to finish

After closing the previous dialog box «Operating time of the Gauss method», summaries of solvability of the reduced system appear (fig. 7).

Fig. 7. The result of the Gauss method

After closing all previous dialog boxes, resulting form, containing several fields for all necessary calculation results, appears on user's screen. By making his choice of method, user receives all results in separate dialog boxes (demonstrated for gradient method with adapted step selection in fig. 8).

Fig. 8. The result of the gradient method with adapted step selection

Upon completion, user is offered the next alternative: either to run the program for another system or to terminate it (fig. 9).

Fig. 9. The end of the program

To close the «Excel» sheet, user has to click the «Exit» button on the main sheet.

Conclusions. Roughly speaking, optimization in mathematical sense is process of finding the best decision. Active life computerization forces mathematical apparatus of optimization to improve, generates new and new optimization problems. Optimization modeling is rather powerful tool, used in various fields, including operations research, engineering, economics, finance, logistics. Along with this, mathematical apparatus of optimization finds its reflection in various classical problems of linear algebra.

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